

Search for New Antimalarials. Part VIII. Synthesis of Some 1,5-Diarylbiquanides

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Twenty 1,5-diarylbiquanide hydrochlorides have been synthesised with a view to studying the variation of antimalarial activity with the change in structure and solubility amongst them.

The discovery of biguanide class of antimalarials, of which proguanil and its 3,4-dichloro analogue¹ showed great promise, marked a distinct advancement in the chemotherapy of malaria. Neelkantau² has observed high antimalarial activity amongst certain 1,5-diarylbiquanides and has also reported that certain biguanides, which are inactive *in vivo*, show considerable activity in inhibiting the respiration of the malarial parasite *in vitro*. The latter observation might be due to the poor solubility of such biguanides in the body fluids.

In view of the above considerations, twenty new 1,5-diarylbiquanides bearing various water-solubilising as well as lipoid-solubilising groups have been synthesised with the idea of studying the variation of antimalarial activity with the change in structure and solubility of such compounds.

The required 1,5-diarylbiquanide hydrochlorides were prepared by condensing different aromatic primary amines with dicyanimide in aqueous solution in presence of hydrochloric acid at reflux temperature. The aqueous solution of dicyanimide was prepared by the interaction of calcium cyanamide and a 50% aqueous solution of cyanogen bromide.

These biguanides were characterised through their picrates. The results of the antimalarial activity will be reported later.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dicyanimide (aqueous solution).—Calcium cyanamide (10.0 g.) was added to a 50% aqueous solution of cyanogen bromide (10.0 g.). The mixture was kept at room temperature overnight, then warmed on a water bath, and filtered hot. The filtrate containing dicyanimide was immediately used for condensation with amines.

Reaction of Dicyanimide with Aromatic Primary Amines.—Metanilic acid (8.0 g.) and HCl (conc., 5 ml) were added to the still warm filtrate containing dicyanimide and the mixture was refluxed for 8 hrs. The hot solution was decolorised with charcoal, filtered, and cooled to deposit crystals, which were collected and recrystallised from hot water to give pure 1, 5-diarylbiquanide hydrochloride.

1. Curd and Rose, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 729; Rose, *Endeavour*, 1946, 18, 65.

2. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 1507.

Naphthionic acid, 3-hydroxynaphthionic acid, sulphanilamide, *p*-aminobenzoic acid, *p*-aminosalicylic acid, *p*-aminophenol, *m*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline, *p*-iodoaniline, 2,4-dichloroaniline, 3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyaniline, 3-chloro-4-bromoaniline, 2-methyl-4-iodoaniline, *p*-anisidine, *p*-phenetidine, *p*-aminobenzamide, ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate, *p*-aminoacetophenone, and *p*-aminoacetanilide were also condensed with dicyanimide in a similar way. Aqueous ethanol was used for recrystallisation of the biguanides, whenever necessary.

Picrates.—The crystalline picrates of the 1, 5-diarylbiguanides were easily obtained by mixing the hot saturated aqueous or ethanolic solutions of the picric acid and the corresponding biguanide hydrochloride and cooling. These were recrystallised from 50% aqueous ethanol. The m.p., yield, and analysis, etc. of the biguanides and their picrates are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Substitution (R).	Biguanide hydrochlorides.				Picrates.			
	M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Pound.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
3-Sulphonyl-	> 290°	82%	15.47	15.58	..	..	..	..
2,3-Benzo-4-sulphonyl-	> 200°	80	12.66	12.74	..	..	..	..
2,3-Benzo-4-sulphonyl-6-hydroxy-	> 290°	80	11.95	12.04	..	..	..	..
4-Amidosulphonyl-	> 290°	73	21.87	21.90	189° (d)	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₁₁ N ₁₀ S ₂	21.89	21.87
4-Carboxy-	234°	77	18.59	18.54	..	..	..	..
3-Hydroxy-4-carboxy-	> 290°	76	17.04	17.10	..	..	..	..
4-Hydroxy-	241° (d)	58	21.71	21.77	178°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₉ N ₈	21.83	21.79
3-Chloro-	245°	68	19.44	19.53	169°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₈ Cl ₂	20.34	20.33
4-Bromo-	259°	76	15.67	15.60	172°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₈ Br ₂	17.41	17.50
4-Iodo-	263-64°	70	12.86	12.93	161-62°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₈ I ₂	15.22	15.26
2,4-Dichloro-	258°	64	16.35	16.38	166°	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₈ Cl ₄	18.00	18.07
3,5-Dibromo-4-hydroxy-	266-37°	56	10.85	10.98	177°	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₉ N ₈ Br ₄	13.45	13.40
3-Chloro-4-bromo-	261°	61	13.51	13.56	173-74°	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₈ Cl ₂ Br ₂	15.75	15.80
2-Methyl-4-iodo-	244°	53	12.26	12.29	162°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₇ N ₈ I ₂	14.68	14.70
4-Methoxy-	256°	80	20.11	20.04	171°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₉ N ₈	20.61	20.65
4-Ethoxy-	248°	75	18.52	18.54	164°	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₈	19.58	19.65
4-Carbamido-	243°	65	26.02	26.10	178-70°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₇ N ₁₀	24.60	24.65
4-Ethoxycarbonyl-	216°	60	16.09	16.15	169-61°	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₁₁ N ₈	17.72	17.89
4-Methylcarbonyl-	252°	57	18.70	18.74	165°	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₉ N ₈	19.39	19.78
4-Acetamido-	231°	64	24.24	24.29	172°	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₉ N ₁₀	23.46	23.49